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INADEQUATE TRAINING OF P.E TEACHERS AND DEARTH OF EQUIPMENT AND FACILITIES AS PREDICTORS OF INEFFECTIVE TEACHING AND LEARNING OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN PUBLIC PRIMARY SCHOOLS OF NGOR-OKPALALGA OF IMO STATE

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out with a view to examining the effect of inadequate training of P.E teachers and dearth of equipment and facilities as predictors for ineffective teaching and learning of physical education in public primary schools in Ngor-Okpala LGA, Imo State. The descriptive survey research design was used for the study. A total of one hundred (100) respondents selected from ten (10) Public Primary Schools that cut across the local government were used for the study. The instrument employed was a questionnaire while the statistical analysis was carried out using chi-square to test the hypotheses at 0.5level of significance. The findings revealed that training of P.E teachers is key in the teaching and learning of PE in public primary schools while provision of equipment and facilities is germane and will go a long way in helping to facilitate effective teaching and learning of PE in public primary schools.

KEYWORDS

Training, Facilities, Equipment, In-effective Teaching

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INTRODUCTION

Physical education is a subject that does not only promote the wellbeing of an individual but also help in developing a sound mind in a sound body and it is an important aspect of the school curriculum. Physical education is taught directly and indirectly. It is taught directly through class instructions and practical while it is taught indirectly through engagement of students in school's annual inter-house sport activities, and other activities.

Primary school is the main domain where teaching of physical education takes place. Adedeji (1985) noted that before the coming of the whiteman, Nigerians practiced several indigenous games such as wrestling, hunting, traditional dance, and many more which serve as recreational activities during their leisure period. According to him, those games formed the basis of their existence and before a child is enrolled in school, he or she has already acquired a lot of sports skills throughout participation in traditional sports. Aghenta (1984) observed that participation in sports involve greater effort. He noted that through sports participation the youths acquire and develop sports knowledge as well as observing the rules and regulations as applied to sports men and women in amateur and professional sports.

Thus, physical education is an instruction in the development and care of the body ranging from simple callisthenic exercise in a course of study to providing training in hygiene, gymnastics and the performance and management of games.(Mgbor,2006) Consequently, Emetarom (2004) submitted that physical education as a term is broad in scope, meaning and content so much that the different definitions have been given to it by different authors. According to Adedeji (1985) physical education is the process of education that concerns activities, which the human body requires for maintenance and development. Mgbor (2006) submitted that physical education is the study of the characteristics of human movements and the effects of the risk activities on the physiological and psychological characteristics of individuals in the social environment. Consequent upon the foregoing, modern day teaching of physical education according to Asiyai(2012) requires the use of instructional material to enhance teaching and learning of the subject in schools. Similarly, Ajayi(1999) and Ogonor(2001) maintained that resource utilization is fundamental in the actualization of effective teaching of physical education in schools. In the same vein, Adeboyeje(2000) and Obiyemi and Abayomi(1995) stressed the need for adequate and effective management of facilities and equipment to achieving a sustainable teaching and learning of physical education in schools.

This study therefore set out to investigate the impact of inadequate training of PE teachers and dearth of equipment and facilities on effective teaching and learning of physical education in public primary schools in Ngor-Okpala LGA,Imo state.

Objectives

The objective of this study is;

1. To determine the effect of inadequate training of teachers on effective teaching and learning of physical education in public primary schools of Ngor-Okpala LGA, Imo state.
2. To determine the effect of dearth of equipment and facilities on effective teaching and learning of physical education in public primary schools of Ngor-Okpala LGA, Imo state.

Statement of Problem

One of the problems affecting the teaching and learning of physical education in public primary schools in the 21st century may not be unconnected with unavailability and use of instructional materials occasioned by poor supply and inadequate training. Public primary schools are

also faced with dearth of equipment and facilities and this is affecting the outcome of teaching and learning process in the primary schools which serve as the foundation for greater academic success. Therefore, the study set out to examine the effect of inadequate training of teachers and dearth of equipment and facilities on effective teaching and learning of physical education in public primary schools in Ngor-Okpala LGA, Imo state.

Research Questions

Answers were sought for the following questions:

1. Will inadequate training of PE teachers have significant effect on effective teaching and learning of physical education in public primary schools of Ngor-Okpala LGA, Imo state.?
2. Will dearth of equipment and facilities have significant effect on effective teaching and learning of physical education in public primary schools of Ngor-Okpala LGA, Imo state.?

Hypotheses

1. Inadequate training of PE teachers will not significantly have effect on effective teaching and learning of physical education in public primary schools of Ngor-Okpala LGA, Imo state.
2. Dearth of equipment and facilities will not significantly have effect on effective teaching and learning of physical education in public primary schools of Ngor-Okpala LGA, Imo state.

METHODOLOGY

Hypothesis 1: Inadequate training of PE teachers will not significantly have effect on effective teaching and learning of physical education in public primary schools of Ngor-Okpala LGA, Imo state.

Table 1: Chi-square table showing Inadequate training of PE teachers will not significantly have effect on teaching and learning of physical education in public primary schools of Ngor-Okpala LGA, Imo state.

	Strongly agree	Agree	Strongly disagree	Disagree	X ² cal	X ² crit	Df	P
Some students do not participate in sport practicals	6 16.7%	7 19.4%	12 33.3%	11 30.6%	25.667	16.919	9	.035
Are there special preferences and facilities to encourage such students to participate	8 22.2%	10 27.8%	12 33.3%	6 16.7%				
has there been improvement in participation of students for practical	13 36.1%	16 44.4%	4 11.1%	3 8.3%				

Do teachers understand their reasons and respect them	5 13.9%	5 13.9%	12 33.3%	14 38.95				
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The table above shows that Inadequate training of PE teachers is significantly perceived as factor affecting the effective teaching and learning of physical education in public primary schools in Ngor-Okpala LGA,Imo state. ($X^2_{cal}=25.667$, $X^2_{crit}=16.919$, $df=9$, $p< 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

The result on table 1 showed that inadequate training of PE teachers will significantly affect the teaching and learning of physical education in public primary schools in Ngor-Okpala LGA, Imo state. This finding is in agreement with Mgbor(2006) who noted that physical education teachers are greatly motivated to teach when given the opportunity to be trained periodically.

Hypothesis 2: Dearth of equipment and facilities will not significantly have effect on teaching and learning of physical education in public primary schools of Ngor-Okpala LGA,Imo state.

Table 2: Chi-square table showing dearth of equipment and facilities will not significantly have effect on teaching and learning of physical education in public primary schools ofNgor-Okpala LGA,Imo state.

	Strongly agree	Agree	Stongly disagree	Disagree	X2cal	X2crit	Df	P
We have all the facilities for physical education practical	15 41.7%	18 50.0%	3 8.3%	-	29.667	12.592	6	.000
Practical rooms are subsets for other purposes in my school	1 2.8%	2 5.6%	13 36.1%	20 55.6%				
All participating students have access to all required equipment for sporting activities	-	-	19 52.8%	17 47.2%				
Students are allowed to use some of the equipment to practice.	16 44,4%	7 19.4%	7 19.4%	6 16.7%				

The table above shows that dearth of equipment and facilities will significantly have effect on teaching and learning of physical education in public primary schools of Ngor-Okpala LGA, Imo state. ($X^2_{cal}=29.667$, $X^2_{crit}12.592$, $df=6$, $p< 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

The result in table 2 revealed that dearth of equipment and facilities will significantly affect the teaching and learning of physical education in public primary schools in Ngor-Okpala LGA, Imo state. The result corroborated Asiyai (2012) who submitted that inadequate equipment and facilities made teaching and learning of physical education difficult. Adebeyeje (2000) noted that the inadequacy of equipment and facilities were major problems facing Nigerian educational system. He submitted that the school facilities are grossly inadequate to match the student's population and the available facilities were poorly maintained. Obiyemi and Abayomi (1995) noted that school facilities enable the teacher to accomplish his/her task as well as help the learner to learn and achieve effectively. Additionally, they emphasized that the availability and proper use of school equipment and facilities can affect the interest of the teacher to teach effectively.

Conclusion

From the foregoing, it can be deduced that the factors been studied is very crucial in the promotion of teaching and learning of physical education in public primary schools. It behooves on government at the local government level to facilitate periodic training for the P.E teachers, provide quality facilities and equipment and see to the provision of instructional materials in quantum to the primary schools teachers and pupils to enhance the teaching and learning of physical education.

Recommendations

In view of the above, this study offers the under listed recommendations:

1. Equipment and Facilities should be made available to enhance teaching and learning of physical education in Public Primary Schools of Ngor-Okpala LGA, Imo State.
2. Qualified and creative PE teachers should be employed as this would help stimulate the interest of students in the subject thereby enhancing their participation in PE.
3. Teachers in Ngor-Okpala LGA should be made to undergo periodic training in the use of instructional material as this would help sharpen their teaching skills and ensure their compliant to 21st century method of teaching Physical Education.

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